

STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESSES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: This article contains a solution to problems aimed at improving the relationship between teachers and students in secondary schools. In addition, what is High Impact Teaching Strategies and their application methods are presented in the article. These High Impact Teaching Strategies (HITS) have been brought together here to support the thousands of increasingly collaborative and evidence-based conversations taking place between teachers in schools each day.

Key words: Framework for Improving Student Outcomes, professional learning communities, school leaders, setting goals, structuring lessons, explicit teaching, worked examples, collaborative learning, multiple exposures, questioning, feedback.

When teachers work together to improve their practice, students learn more. This simple yet powerful idea is at the heart of effective schools. Collaboration builds collective responsibility for constantly improving teaching practice and so student learning. The challenge for teachers and schools is to develop a shared understanding of what excellent practice looks like. While it will not look the same in every classroom, there are some instructional practices that evidence suggests work well in most.

The HITS will support teachers at every career stage. Each strategy is accompanied by two examples. The examples show teachers how to adapt the HITS to different learning goals and needs, and to respond to different school contexts. For beginning teachers, the HITS are a bank of reliable instructional practices they can use with confidence. For experienced teachers, this resource can add to their

understanding of the HITS they are already using, and suggest new ways to use them in the classroom. Even teachers highly familiar with the HITS will benefit from this resource as they pursue mastery of these valuable instructional practices through practice, reflection, shared observation and feedback.

Professional Learning Communities

Confined to individual teachers and classrooms, the HITS will not contribute to the collective efficacy that marks out high-performing schools. In these schools, teachers come together to pool their knowledge of effective teaching into a collaborative approach to planning, implementing and monitoring teaching interventions.

By using the HITS to build their pool of knowledge, these professional learning communities can anchor their interventions in evidence-based practices and so increase the likelihood of those interventions being effective.

School leaders

For school leaders the HITS are a professional learning opportunity. The HITS are linked to each other, and connected to a broader repertoire of teacher skills and knowledge. They can be connected to collaboration between teachers in professional learning communities and integrated into classroom and school planning around curriculum, instruction and assessment.

Understanding the inter-dependencies and developing a whole of practice approach is complex work for teachers that requires classroom embedded professional learning and a supportive high performance learning culture in a school. A sustained focus on HITS can be supported by coaching, modeling, observation and feedback to ensure widespread use of successful teaching practices.

Setting Goals. Lessons have clear learning intentions with goals that clarify what success looks like. Lesson goals always explain what students need to understand, and what they must be able to do. This helps the teacher to plan learning activities, and helps students understand what is required

Structuring Lessons. A lesson structure maps teaching and learning that occurs in class. Sound lesson structures reinforce routines, scaffold learning via specific

steps/activities. They optimize time on task and classroom climate by using smooth transitions. Planned sequencing of teaching and learning activities stimulates and maintains engagement by linking lesson and unit learning

Explicit Teaching. When teachers adopt explicit teaching practices, they clearly show students what to do and how to do it. The teacher decides on learning intentions and success criteria, makes them transparent to students, and demonstrates them by modelling. The teacher checks for understanding and at the end of each lesson revisits what was covered and ties it all together (Hattie, 2009).

Worked Examples. A worked example demonstrates the steps required to complete a task or solve a problem. By scaffolding the learning, worked examples support skill acquisition and reduce a learner’s cognitive load. The teacher presents a worked example and explains each step. Later, students can use worked examples during independent practice, and to review and embed new knowledge.

Feedback. Feedback informs a student and/or teacher about the student’s performance relative to learning goals. Feedback redirects or refocuses teacher and student actions so the student can align effort and activity with a clear outcome that leads to achieving a learning goal. Teachers and peers can provide formal or informal feedback. It can be oral, written, formative or assumptive. Whatever its form, it comprises specific advice a student can use to improve performance

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